

Use of ladle furnace slag as filler replacement in magnesium oxychloride cement: Towards sustainable 3D-printable building composites

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ABSTRACT

In response to the global demand for CO₂ emissions reduction, Portland cement (PC) replacement with more eco-friendly materials has been focused on in material studies. One of the studied alternatives is magnesium oxychloride cement (MOC), which offers excellent mechanical properties and lower production temperatures. The ecological impact of MOC alone is significant, but if we incorporate waste material as a filler replacement in MOC composites, we can decrease overall emissions even more. In this paper, we focused on the development of an eco-friendly material with a safely incorporated ladle furnace slag (SL). Firstly, the SL was characterized by numerous analytical methods (XRF, XRD, SEM, EDS, STA-MS) to attain knowledge about its elemental and phase composition. In the following step, MOC composite materials with SL used as a silica sand partial replacement were prepared by casting. Such prepared materials were then characterized by XRF, XRD, SEM, EDS, and MIP. Furthermore, their structural and mechanical properties were assessed. Based on the obtained results, an optimized composition of mixtures was used for 3D printing to demonstrate the suitability of this material for this purpose. Finally, X-ray computed micro-tomography imaging was used to study the quality of printed cubes, in particular porosity and the amount of macroscopic defects. This paper presents an innovative approach in which waste SL from steel production can replace silica sand filler in significant quantities, demonstrating that such a designed material is suitable for additive manufacturing.

1. Introduction

Steel slag, a by-product of steel manufacturing, is produced in large amounts worldwide and ranks among the major industrial by-products by volume. With an estimated annual production between 190 and 290 million tons, it accounts for approximately 10–15 % of total crude steel output [1]. In the Czech Republic alone, around 1.0–1.2 million tons of steel slag and an additional 1.5–2.0 million tons of blast furnace slag are produced each year [2,3]. Notably, nearly all of this slag is already reused, primarily in the construction sector, which highlights

the country's success in implementing circular economy principles [4]. Traditionally, steel slag has found wide application in civil engineering, used as a replacement for natural aggregate in concrete, asphalt, and road base layers, and also as a supplementary cementitious material [5–8]. Its dense and angular structure improves mechanical performance [9], while its hydraulic properties, provided the phase composition is suitable, enable partial cementitious activity when finely ground [10,11]. When incorporated into blended cements, ground granulated blast furnace slag can partially replace Portland cement clinker, thereby reducing the carbon intensity of the final product [12].

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Table 1

Compositions of prepared samples (g), SL is ladle furnace slag.

	MgO	MgCl ₂ •6H ₂ O	Water	Silica sand			SL		
				0–0.5	0.5–1	1–2	0–0.5	0.5–1	1–2
MOC-REF	177.48	179.04	111.06	177.48	177.48	177.48	–	–	–
MOC-SL-50	177.48	179.04	111.06	88.74	88.74	88.74	88.74	88.74	88.74
MOC-SL-3D	88.73	89.52	55.52	–	–	–	246.70	–	–

Although current applications of slag are widely established, it is desirable to seek higher value utilization pathways, particularly for ladle slags from secondary metallurgy.

Steel slag can be simply represented by CaO-MgO-SiO₂-FeO quaternary system. The chemical composition of slags from the basic oxygen furnace (BOF) typically includes 30–55 % CaO (of which up to 12 % may be present as free lime), 8–20 % SiO₂, 1–6 % Al₂O₃, 5–15 % MgO, and up to 35 % Fe₂O₃. The composition of electric arc furnace (EAF) slags depends on the type of scrap used, the flux additions, and the operating conditions during steelmaking; typical values include 35–60 % CaO, 15–30 % FeO, 9–20 % SiO₂, 2–9 % Al₂O₃, and 5–15 % MgO. During the steel making, different types of slags can be produced depending on the furnace type – blast furnace slag and ladle furnace slag (SL). SL is a by-product of steelmaking generated during the secondary refining of steel in a ladle furnace. SL generally have lower iron oxide content compared to blast furnace slags but often exhibit higher concentrations of CaO and Al₂O₃. However, the application of steel slag, especially SL, in engineering has been limited on account CaO and MgO [13,14]. One of the main limitations to the wider use of steel slag is its volumetric instability, which is related to the presence of reactive, thermodynamically unstable phases that undergo hydration and transformation. The most common cause of this instability is the presence of free calcium oxide (f-CaO) and free magnesium oxide (f-MgO), which are not fully bound in stable mineral phases. Upon contact with water, free MgO hydrates to form magnesium hydroxide (Mg(OH)₂, brucite), and free CaO forms calcium hydroxide (Ca(OH)₂, portlandite). In the presence of CO₂, these hydroxides further carbonate to form magnesium carbonate (MgCO₃) and calcium carbonate (CaCO₃) [15–18].

In parallel with the increasing demand for sustainable construction materials, magnesium oxychloride cement (MOC) has re-emerged as a promising alternative binder to ordinary Portland cement (OPC) [19, 20]. MOC, originally developed by Stanislas Sorel in the 19th century, is formed by the reaction of MgO with a concentrated MgCl₂ solution [21]. Compared to OPC, MOC requires significantly lower calcination temperature (~1450 °C vs. ~700–800 °C), and thus its production results in approximately 50 % lower CO₂ emissions [22]. MOC systems develop a dense matrix composed primarily of stable crystalline phases such as 5Mg(OH)₂•MgCl₂•8H₂O (Phase 5) and 3Mg(OH)₂•MgCl₂•8H₂O (Phase 3), responsible for the material's high compressive strength, which can range from 50 to over 100 MPa depending on formulation [23–25]. In addition to its mechanical strength, MOC exhibits excellent fire resistance, low thermal conductivity, and strong adhesion to diverse substrates, making it an attractive material for flooring, fireproof panels, and specialized construction applications [26–28]. A major limitation arises from the poor water resistance of Phases 5 and 3: upon exposure to moisture, they decompose into Mg(OH)₂ and MgCl₂, which ultimately causes deterioration of the MOC binder as a whole [29–32].

The slag incorporation brings a positive effect on the traditionally poor water resistance of MOC. Studies have demonstrated that the synergistic effect of SL addition combined with carbonation curing of MOC in a CO₂-rich environment significantly enhances water stability by the reaction with CO₂, as well as the refinement of the pore structure with SL [33–35]. The carbonation promotes the transformation of periclase and brucite from MOC, as well as free lime from SL, into insoluble carbonate phases, resulting in a matrix less prone to degradation in wet conditions [20]. Softening coefficients greater than 1.0 have been reported for slag-modified, carbonated MOC composites, indicating that

full or even improved strength is achieved after immersion [33]. Moreover, carbonation curing not only improves durability but also enables meaningful CO₂ sequestration, thereby reducing the overall carbon footprint of the material. Even though a decreasing trend in mechanical properties was observed with the incorporation of steel slag, the reported strengths commonly reach values between 95 and 120 MPa after 28 days, demonstrating that slag-modified MOC can meet or exceed the mechanical requirements for structural applications [36,37]. In addition to water resistance enhancement, the introduction of steel slag in general has been shown to refine the microstructure of the cement matrix. The latent hydraulic activity of the SL promotes the formation of secondary binding phases, such as calcium silicate hydrate (C–S–H) gels and calcium-magnesium carbonates, which fill pores, reduce capillary porosity, and densify the microstructure [33,36]. Fine fractions of SL typically contain γ-C₂S, which does not exhibit binding properties in water under normal conditions. However, in the presence of alkaline activators, these fine particles can demonstrate significant binding activity even at laboratory temperatures. The finer the particle size of the SL, the more pronounced its binding potential becomes [38,39].

Despite this promising potential, the systematic experimental study of MOC composites incorporating SL remains limited, particularly in terms of evaluating their physical and mechanical properties under practical curing conditions. Moreover, very little is known about the applicability of such systems in emerging technologies such as additive manufacturing. From an environmental perspective, the valorization of SL – a major industrial by-product – contributes to circular economy objectives, minimizes waste disposal challenges, and reduces dependence on high-purity magnesia. An emerging application area is additive manufacturing. The inherent rapid setting and strength gain of MOC align well with the demands of 3D printing, particularly for layer-by-layer construction. Researchers have shown that steel slag-based binders, activated by MgO and cured via CO₂, can be used to print structural elements with good mechanical performance and integrated carbon capture [40]. While still in its early stages, the combination of MOC, SL, and 3D printing represents a forward-looking approach to sustainable construction.

In this study, we investigate the incorporation of SL into MOC composites, focusing on their structural performance in both cast and additively manufactured forms. The aim is to assess not only the mechanical and microstructural implications of SL addition but also the feasibility of processing such mixtures via extrusion-based 3D printing. In summary, SL presents a significant opportunity for advancing sustainable, low-carbon construction. Its incorporation into MOC composites offers a technically and economically viable pathway for producing durable, high-performance binders while valorizing industrial waste. Coupled with the advantages of CO₂ curing and the potential for 3D printing, this approach contributes to broader efforts aimed at achieving a circular economy and reducing carbon footprints.

2. Experimental

2.1. Experimental setup and process description

Firstly, SL was ground and sieved to produce finer fractions in sizes of 0–0.5, 0.5–1, and 1–2 mm to replace silica sand filler with the identical particle size distribution. A small amount of raw SL was completely milled to a fine fraction for further analysis.

Fig. 1. Scheme of the experimental work.

Afterward, the preparation of MOC composites took place. SL was used as a partial replacement of a silica sand filler. The MOC composite samples were prepared using MgO (p.a. purity, Penta, Czech Republic), MgCl₂•6H₂O (p.a. purity, Lachner, Czech Republic), tap water, silica sand (Filtrační písky, spol. s.r.o., Czech Republic), and SL (Třinecké železářny, a.s., Czech Republic). The silica sand and SL were used in size fractions of 0–0.5, 0.5–1, and 1–2 mm in the weight ratio of 1:1:1. The composition of the prepared mixtures is shown in Table 1. The designation of the cast samples is the following: MOC-REF is a reference sample using only silica sand as a filler, MOC-SL-50 is a sample in which the silica sand is partially replaced in the amount of 50 wt% by SL. After mixing, the fresh mixtures were cast into molds (40 mm × 40 mm × 160 mm), where they remained for 1 day before being demolded and cured for an additional 27 days. During both curing stages, the temperature was maintained at 23 ± 2 °C, and the relative humidity was 50 ± 5 %. Following the curing period, the MOC samples were analyzed for their phase composition, chemical composition, microstructure, and basic structural, and mechanical properties. Furthermore, an additional mixture (MOC-SL-3D) was prepared using the same procedure, with only the 0–0.5 mm fraction of SL as the filler, intended for 3D printing. The amount of SL was determined experimentally to achieve optimal rheological properties for the printing process. The overall process is schematically visualized in Fig. 1.

2.2. Characterization techniques

The raw material SL was thoroughly characterized using a range of analytical techniques. The chemical composition was determined using energy-dispersive X-ray fluorescence spectroscopy (ED-XRF) on the SUPERMINI 200. The mineralogical composition of samples was evaluated using X-Ray diffraction (XRD) analysis on the X-Ray diffractometer MiniFlex 600 equipped 270 with a Co tube and D/teX Ultra detector (CoKα = 1.789 Å). The XRD patterns were recorded in a 5–90° 2θ range with a scanning rate of 5°/min. Simultaneous thermal analysis coupled with mass spectrometry (STA-MS) was employed to investigate the thermal behavior of the material. The sample was measured in a dynamic air atmosphere. The macro- and microstructure of the sample surface were examined using optical microscopy (OM) and scanning electron microscopy (SEM). Basic physical properties, including loose bulk density, specific density, and water absorption, were measured. In addition, volume stability was evaluated.

Another important aspect of determining SL stability is the evaluation of changes in volume that occur during its utilization, for which an

effective methodology was developed. Prior to testing, the SL sample was processed to a grain size of less than 3 mm, sieved, and dried at 50 °C until a constant weight was achieved. After drying, the SL was immediately used to prevent moisture reabsorption. The experiment was conducted under controlled laboratory conditions at a temperature of 20 ± 3 °C. Reaction stainless-steel cylindrical vessels, equipped with filter paper and filled with samples up to 2/3 of their volume, were hermetically connected to a water reservoir and embedded in sand to ensure thermal stability. The sample surfaces were leveled and covered with nylon lids. Demineralized water was poured into the reservoir so that its level in the reaction vessel reached at least the top of the sample. During the test, the water level was maintained between the sample surface and the lid level to compensate for evaporation. Measurements were recorded every 2 min (sample height with 0.01 mm accuracy, temperature with 0.1 °C accuracy). The test was considered complete once the relative volume change over a 24-hour interval stabilized within ±0.2 % [41,42].

Casted and cured composites were analyzed using the same set of techniques. However, for XRD, a Bruker D2 Phaser (CuKα = 1.5418 Å) was used. Furthermore, the fundamental structural properties of the cast samples, including dry bulk density, specific density, and total open porosity, were measured. Microstructural characteristics, such as total pore volume, average pore size, and pore size distribution curves, were obtained by mercury intrusion porosimetry (MIP). In addition, mechanical properties such as compressive strength, flexural strength, and Young's modulus were determined. Employed analytical methods and tests are described in detail in our previous work [43].

For the purpose of 3D printing of selected models, a 3D printer Tronxy, specialized for printing materials based on ceramic clays, or mixtures of ceramic clays with other materials, was used. The used 3D printer is equipped with an automatic feeding device, conveying the printed material through a cylindrical tray with a volume of about 750 ml. The mass is conveyed through a passage from the tray via a 6 mm diameter polyethylene tube to the print head (extruder) and pushed by a screw conveyor through a 2.5 mm diameter nozzle to the printing bed. The height of the bottom and top layers of the models printed for this research was 1 mm, and the height of the successive intermediate layers was 1.3 mm. The printing speed of the bottom and top layers of the model was 20 mm/s, while the printing speed of each intermediate layer was 40 mm/s. The width of the individual print lines was set to 2 mm, so that the internal space of the printed model was 100 % filled with the printed material.

For the X-ray computed micro-tomography (μXCT) scanning

Fig. 2. Schematic diagram of X-ray computed micro-tomography.

Fig. 3. Original form of SL.

procedure, the acceleration voltage of 100 kV and a target current of 180 μ A, together with a 500 μ m Copper filter [31], were used to obtain as high-quality an image of the radiograms as possible. Altogether, μ XCT scans consisted of 2868 equiangular projections with 600 ms acquisition time. Including the positioning and read-out time, each tomographic scan took \sim 35 mins. A similar μ XCT setup was used in [44], and it could be easily mounted with a loading device for either bending [45] or compression testing [46,47]. The schematic diagram of μ XCT can be seen in Fig. 2.

The reconstruction of individual 3D images was performed using a Feldkamp–Davis–Kress (FDK) filtered back projection reconstruction algorithm [48] implemented in VGSTUDIO MAX 2025.1 (Volume Graphics, Germany), constructing 3D data matrices with dimensions of $1536 \times 1536 \times 1944$ voxels, producing a voxel size of 25.6 μ m.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Characterization of ladle furnace slag

Fig. 3 shows the original form of SL. The fine SL powder was characterized in terms of phase and elemental composition, thermal stability, and volume stability. The chemical composition of SL was characterized by XRF (see Table 2). Obtained composition was recalculated to oxides; however, some elements such as iron are present in it

metallic form. The high content of CaO (52.94 %) and a significant amount of Fe₂O₃ (16.92 %) indicate a strongly basic nature of the SL, which is crucial for sulfur removal and other impurity binding during refining processes. The presence of SiO₂ (12.14 %), Al₂O₃ (5.83 %), and a smaller amount of MgO (2.82 %) suggests the formation of complex oxide phases—typically silicates and aluminosilicates. The notable levels of MnO (2.76 %) and Cr₂O₃ (0.59 %) point to the transfer of alloying elements from the processed steel, which is common in SL formed during the refining of high-alloy or stainless steels. The contents of SO₃ (1.24 %) and P₂O₅ (0.66 %) may indicate residues of unoxidized components or the influence of additive materials used during refining. Overall, this represents a typical composition of basic SL [49].

The sample was ignited at a temperature of 1000 °C, and its weight was monitored until a constant weight was reached. Subsequently, the loss on ignition (LOI) was determined and expressed in weight percent. The 3.84 % LOI of SL indicates the release of chemically bound water and carbon dioxide, mainly due to the presence of hydrated and carbonated phases, as further confirmed by the presented phase analysis. Overall, the composition indicates that SL has potential for use as a hydraulically active material, though its expansive behavior and compositional variability must be carefully considered.

Major elements were confirmed by ED-XRF measurement; their elemental maps are shown in Fig. 3 (see below). Carbon, which cannot be detected by XRF, was detected through this method in the content of approximately 4.7 wt%. All the detected elements are homogeneously distributed throughout the sample. In Fig. 4, the microstructure of SL obtained from SEM is shown, confirming the SL morphology of a fine powder with relatively homogeneous particle size distribution.

Table 3 and Fig. 5 summarize all phases determined in the SL sample in its original form and after the hydration process. In the original SL samples, the main identified phases are dicalcium silicates in both β (larnite) and γ (calcio-olivine) modifications, along with brownmillerite, wüstite, mayenite, periclase, calcite, and gehlenite. In the SL sample exposed to intensive hydration, the γ -C₂S phase, as well as non-hydraulic wüstite, brownmillerite, and gehlenite, remained preserved. A significant increase in calcite and γ -dicalcium silicate peaks was observed. As a

Table 2
Chemical composition of SL determined by XRF (as oxides).

Oxides wt%	CaO	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	MgO	Fe ₂ O ₃	MnO	SO ₃	TiO ₂	P ₂ O ₅	Cr ₂ O ₃	LOI
	52.94	12.14	5.83	2.82	16.92	2.76	1.24	0.26	0.66	0.59	3.84

Fig. 4. SEM micrographs (top) and EDS elemental maps (bottom) of SL.

Table 3

Phase analysis of sample SL before and after hydration.

SL before hydration process			SL after hydration process		
No.	Phases		No.	Phases	
1	γ -dicalcium silicate	Ca_2SiO_4	1	γ -dicalcium silicate	Ca_2SiO_4
2	β -dicalcium silicate	Ca_2SiO_4	3	brownmillerite	$\text{Ca}_2(\text{Al}, \text{Fe})_2\text{O}_5$
3	brownmillerite	$\text{Ca}_2(\text{Al}, \text{Fe})_2\text{O}_5$	7	gehlenite	$\text{Ca}_2\text{Al}(\text{SiAl})\text{O}_7$
5	mayenite	$\text{Ca}_{12}\text{Al}_{14}\text{O}_{33}$	9	calcite	CaCO_3
6	periclase	MgO	11	wüstite	FeO
7	gehlenite	$\text{Ca}_2\text{Al}(\text{SiAl})\text{O}_7$	12	katoit	$\text{Ca}_3\text{Al}_2(\text{OH})_{12}$
9	calcite	CaCO_3	16	brucite	$\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$
11	wüstite	FeO	19	grossular	$\text{Ca}_3\text{Al}_2(\text{SiO}_4)_3$
12	katoit	$\text{Ca}_3\text{Al}_2(\text{OH})_{12}$			

result of the reaction with water, brucite was formed.

Thermal stability was determined using STA-MS (see Fig. 6). The overall weight loss was approximately 6 wt%, which is slightly higher in comparison to previously described annealing experiments. During the heating, three major endothermic effects were observed. The first one, at approximately 100 °C, was associated with water release, due to moisture evaporation. The second major effect at 300 °C is also associated with water release. This water was present in the form of crystalline water in mixed hydroxides (e.g., $\text{Ca}_3\text{Al}_2(\text{OH})_{12}$) [50]. The third effect at 700 °C was caused by the decomposition of calcite, which was confirmed by MS [51]. Interestingly, according to the TG curve, starting from 750 °C, the weight of the samples started to slowly rise. This effect can be due to the partial oxidation of metallic iron present in the sample.

The graphical data presented in Fig. 7 illustrate the volume stability of the tested SL according to the procedure described above. The accompanying temperature curves (red) reflect the testing conditions, specifically the temperature of the sand bath, in which the experiment was conducted, and the temperature of the water affecting the SL during the experiment. These temperature values remained nearly constant throughout the testing period with downward fluctuations caused by the

Fig. 5. Diffractogram of A) original phases of SL and B) SL phases after hydration process (CoK α).

Fig. 6. STA-MS of SL in air.

addition of demineralized water into the reservoir. From the volume change graph, it is evident that the SL undergoes a hydration reaction, which is closely related to its phase composition. Granulometry, specifically the distribution of particle size fractions, also has a significant impact on the volume stability. During the first three days of exposure to the water environment in the volume stability test, the SL exhibited relatively stable volumetric behavior. Subsequently, a gradual increase in the volume of the sample was recorded, which reached a total volume change of 7 vol.% after 20 days of immersion in a water environment under elevated temperature.

The authors [42] studied the volume change over 13 days of selected

types of steelmaking slags. The MgO content in these slags was 4.1 %, 39 %, 9.79 %, and 4 %, respectively, and all slags had a CaO content above 45 %. The observed volume changes were 3 %, 286 %, 40 %, and 6 %, respectively. Based on the analyses and observations, it was found that hydrated phases formed during hydration in all samples—mainly portlandite (Ca(OH) $_2$) and brucite (Mg(OH) $_2$). The sample with the largest volume increase also contained a significant amount of β -C $_2$ S (dicalcium silicate), in addition to these oxides. In a similar test [18], the authors focused on the slag expansion over a period of 16 days the observed volume changes of the three BOF slag samples ranged between 7 and 13 %.

Fig. 7. The volume change of SL after 20 day of hydration process.

Fig. 8. Diffractograms of MOC composite samples obtained by XRD (CuK α).

3.2. Characterization of composites

The phase composition of the MOC composite samples was determined using XRD and can be seen in Fig. 8. Both of the prepared samples contained MOC Phase 5 ($\text{Mg}_3(\text{OH})_5\text{Cl}\cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, ICDD 04–014–8836) [52] and silica sand SiO_2 (Quartz, ICDD 01–085–0795) [53]. Because of the amorphous nature of SL, only major reflections of Ca_2SiO_4 (ICDD 04–016–5413) are visible in the diffractogram. In the sample MOC-SL-50, $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$ (brucite, ICDD 04–015–4256) was identified. According to Rietveld refinement, the brucite content was approx. 13 wt %. This effect was caused by a reaction of SL and MgCl_2 , resulting in an incomplete formation of phase 5. The presence of brucite can negatively influence the mechanical properties of the prepared composite.

The fracture surfaces of MOC-REF and MOC-SL-50 were examined with respect to their microstructure using OM and SEM combined with

EDS mapping. The results are presented in Figs. 9 and 10. In both MOC-REF and MOC-SL-50 samples, silica sand grains are visible, exhibiting a range of colors from white to brown and gray. In the SL-containing samples, black SL grains are also apparent, and the overall matrix color changes from white to light gray. No defects were observed in the samples under optical microscopy.

The SEM micrographs (Fig. 10) reveal a compact structure of the prepared composites, with no visible defects or abnormalities. At a higher magnification, the characteristic needle-like crystals of MOC Phase 5 were clearly observed. These needles measured approximately 1–6 μm in length and around 0.5 μm in width [54]. The fracture surfaces were further analyzed using EDS, with the resulting elemental maps presented in Fig. 11. Both samples contained Mg, O, Cl, Si, and C. The presence of Mg, O, and Cl corresponds to the chemical composition of MOC Phase 5 ($5\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2\cdot\text{MgCl}_2\cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$). Silicon originates from either

Fig. 9. Micrographs of MOC composite samples obtained from OM.

Fig. 10. Micrographs of MOC composite samples obtained from SEM.

Fig. 11. Elemental maps of prepared samples obtained using EDS.

Table 4
Structural properties of 28-day composites.

	Dry bulk density ($\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$)	Specific density ($\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$)	Total open porosity (%)
MOC-REF	2053±8	2255±1	8.95±0.35
MOC-SL-50	1965±15	2371±2	17.12±0.65

silica sand or the added SL. In samples containing SL, Al and Ca were also detected, consistent with the previously described elemental composition of SL.

Fundamental structural parameters of composites, together with their standard deviation, are summarized in Table 4. The 50 % substitution of silica sand by SL significantly affected the structural properties of cured composites. The reduction in the dry bulk density of about 4.3 % was followed by significantly increased total open porosity and enhanced specific density. The overall increase in porosity was approximately 91.3 %, and that of specific density was 5.1 %. The results

of specific density correlate well with the higher density of SL ($3349 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) as compared to that of silica sand ($2637 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$). The observed increase in specific density may also be attributed to the expansion of SL within the fresh composite. This expansion could induce internal stresses that contribute to matrix shrinkage. Simultaneously, it may promote the formation or enlargement of pores within the matrix, thereby altering the overall microstructure and affecting the composite's physical properties as documented below.

Incremental and cumulative pore size distribution curves are plotted in Fig. 12. In addition, volume fractions of pores of specific diameter ranges are shown in Fig. 13. The coarsening of porous structure is well visible in both gel and capillary pores, whereas the capillary pores affecting the mechanical strength and bulk water ingress were dominantly represented. In the MOC-SL-50 sample, the shift in pore size distribution to the pores of higher diameter is quite apparent, which corresponds with total open porosity data and microstructural parameters given in Table 5. Total pore volume increased by 86.1 % and average pore diameter by 70.5 % as compared to the control composite MOC-REF.

The mechanical properties of the composites are summarized in

Fig. 12. Pore size distribution: a) cumulative curves, b) incremental curves.

Fig. 13. Pore volume of specific diameter range.

Table 5
Microstructural properties of 28-day composites.

	Total pore volume (kg·m ⁻³)	Average pore diameter (kg·m ⁻³)
MOC-REF	0.0441	0.0200
MOC-SL-50	0.0821	0.0341

Table 6
Mechanical properties of 28-day composites.

	Compressive strength (MPa)	Flexural strength (MPa)	Young's modulus (GPa)
MOC-REF	74.8 ± 1.1	16.4 ± 0.6	37.4 ± 0.8
MOC-SL-50	48.1 ± 0.3	13.2 ± 0.2	25.8 ± 0.6

Table 6. The standard deviation calculated based on the measurement of 6 samples is also presented. The incorporation of the industrial by-product SL into the composite mixture resulted in a reduction of all

Fig. 14. Photography of a 3D-printed MOC-SL-3D sample – a) and b) – 3D reconstructed volume using μ XCT data.

Fig. 15. 2D cross sections of 3D printed sample – a) X-Y plane, b) – Y-Z plane and c) – X-Z plane.

evaluated mechanical parameters, which aligns with the previously discussed porosity data and phase composition. The presence of brucite in MOC-SL-50, thus incomplete precipitation of phase 5, was the reason for its lower mechanical resistance as compared to the control mix. However, it is important to highlight that 50 % of natural silica sand—currently a scarce and increasingly difficult-to-obtain resource—was successfully replaced by an industrial by-product. This substitution not only enhances the sustainability of the material but also addresses the growing issue of natural aggregate shortages, driven by extensive exploitation, stricter environmental regulations, and the gradual depletion of accessible natural reserves.

From a technical perspective, the achieved mechanical performance, particularly the compressive strength of 48 MPa, is sufficiently high for use in load-bearing structural applications, such as load-bearing columns, concrete walls, prefabricated and prestressed elements [55]. Furthermore, the attained Young's modulus indicates an adequate stiffness level suitable for practical use in construction. These findings demonstrate the potential of incorporating alternative raw materials as functional and environmentally responsible substitutes for natural aggregates in modern construction composites.

3.3. Characterization of 3D printed composite sample

Building on previous findings from the MOC-SL-50 formulation and newly acquired insights, a new MOC composition incorporating SL (designated as MOC-SL-3D) was developed to achieve properties

suitable for 3D printing. The initial attempt to 3D print a cube using this formulation is shown in Fig. 14a, whereas Fig. 14b displays the 3D reconstructed volume from μ XCT data.

Analysis of μ XCT data revealed a considerable amount of unfilled volume corresponding to the printing process. The unfilled volume is rather in-plane and diagonally oriented following the movement of the horizontal layer stacking direction during the extrusion of the material. This volume is located in the upper part (high Z-coordinate) of the 3D-printed sample and appears as an intralayer disconnection; see Figs. 15a, b, and c.

Furthermore, the analysis of 2D cross sections discovered three cracks, increasing in size at the bottom of the sample and growing towards its upper edge. The major crack is located in the middle of the base of the sample and is growing diagonally toward its top edge. This crack causes intra- and interlayer damage, which is not related to the material's extrusion but rather to drying shrinkage; see Figs. 15a, b, and c.

Using 3D CT data, one can quantitatively study the material's heterogeneity, such as pore and crack space, using gray-scale threshold-based algorithms for the identification of solid and air. In this case, an Otsu's [56] approach to thresholding local gray values due to noise was utilized. This approach allows for the analysis of local variation of porosity [44,46], a porosity profile quantification along the arbitrary direction in the reconstructed volume, and mainly to separate individual identified pores as a separate volume, including calculation of morphological characterisation.

The results of this analysis are usually presented as individual pores

Fig. 16. Axonometric view of the obtained pore space of the 3D printed cube of a) top view, and b) bottom view.

Fig. 17. Results of morphological analysis obtained from CT data.

and the cracks coloured according to their calculated volume. It should be noted that porosity calculation from CT data is capable of detecting pores larger than the spatial resolution of $25.6 \mu\text{m}/\text{voxel}$; smaller pores are considered noise. The pore space obtained from the 3D printed sample is shown in Fig. 16.

The initial investigation of the pore space, as presented in Fig. 16a, discovers four shrinkage cracks located at the base of the sample. Identified cracks are more visible in Fig. 16b, in which the growth of the diagonal crack can be seen. Moreover, the pore space analysis revealed equally distributed pores in each extruded layer. The total porosity calculated from CT data is 0.5 %. The previously discussed unfilled volume is again located in the upper part of the sample and is depicted in green in Fig. 16.

Performed analysis allows for morphological quantification of each identified pore, typically by using sphericity and an equivalent diameter. The sphericity is a quantity characterising the pore shape, whereas the equivalent diameter is related to an ideal sphere with the same volume as the identified pore. This way, it simplifies complex, irregular pore shapes to a single comparable number. The results of the morphological analysis are presented as sphericity versus equivalent diameter in Fig. 17.

The calculated sphericity in Fig. 17 indicates that the majority of the pores identified have a compact shape (sphericity > 0.7), as well as

highly irregular pores (sphericity < 0.2) are present. These irregular volumes are again considered to be either cracks or unfilled voids.

4. Conclusions

This work explored the use of ladle furnace slag as a partial replacement for silica sand in MOC composites, aiming to create a more sustainable building material suitable for 3D printing. Based on the presented findings, several conclusions can be drawn:

- The replacement of 50 % of natural silica sand with SL was proven not only feasible, but also meaningful in terms of sustainability. The prepared composite manifested a decreased environmental footprint compared to conventional materials, while giving new life to a widely available by-product from the steel industry.
- As expected, incorporating SL increased porosity and reduced mechanical performance due to the formation of brucite and incomplete development of MOC Phase 5. Even so, the final composite reached a compressive strength of 48 MPa, which remains suitable for structural use in many construction applications.
- The developed MOC-SL-3D mixture was successfully extruded using a 3D printer. The printed samples showed some challenges, such as interlayer cracks and small unfilled volumes, especially toward the top of the print. These were likely caused by drying shrinkage rather than problems with the extrusion itself. Importantly, the total porosity remained very low (0.5 %), and the overall print quality indicates that the material has real potential for additive manufacturing, with room for further optimization.

Data availability

According to OA principles selected raw data can be found at ZENODO [10.5281/zenodo.15826783](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15826783).

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Ondřej Jankovský: Writing – original draft, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Petr Lodňánek:** Writing – original draft, Investigation, Data curation. **Anna-Marie Lauermannová:** Writing – original draft, Investigation, Data curation. **Adéla Jiríčková:** Writing – original draft, Investigation, Data curation. **Jozef Vlček:** Writing – original draft, Investigation, Data curation. **Hana Ovčáčiková:** Writing – original draft, Investigation, Data curation. **Michaela Topinková:** Writing – original draft, Investigation, Data curation. **Petra Maierová:** Writing – original draft, Investigation, Data curation.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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